

Comparative analysis of calculation methods for correct thermal resistance of construction elements made of steel structure

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Summary

Energy performance of buildings is directly influenced by building envelope efficiency, that is on its turn affected by thermal bridging. Global there are different appliances used for assessment of energy performance of buildings, that take into consideration thermal bridges effect by different degrees of accuracy, in order to obtain more realistic results (A. Iacob, M. Pruteanu, A.A. Ciobanu, 2011). In Romania the regulations provide a specific minimum thermal resistance for building elements "R'min". This index takes into account possible thermal bridges present in the system and has to fulfill the requirement of energy efficiency. Corrected thermal resistance values (R') of each building element must be less than its normal value, a value that is reflected in standards .

This paper presents a comparison between values obtained using manual and automatic calculation methods, to determine corrected thermal resistance in constructive solutions consisting of steel columns with closure of masonry, according to various regulations in force in our country. Manual calculations are conducted with due standards "C107-3/2005 - Appendix H and J", "SR EN ISO 10211 Thermal bridges in building construction", "Methodology for calculating energy performance of buildings MC001/2006", and the automatic calculations are made using UNORM program.

Analysing the influence of using these numerical methods in corrected thermal resistance assessment, allows us to lay down some useful conclusions concerning the building energy certification and regulation activity and in pointing out future research direction.

Keywords: *performance, thermal resistance, thermal bridges, numerical methods*

1. Introduction

The main document of European legislation on energy efficiency in construction Energy Performance of Building Directive (EPBD) aims encourage improvements in the energy performance of buildings, taking into account the local climatic requirements hygrothermal comfort and economic efficiency. Results of the implementation of this Directive legislation on energy performance of buildings are present in all Member States European Union, by increasing the quality and efficiency for thermal protection new buildings, but also for the rehabilitation (Arkesteijn K., Dijk D., 2008).

Almost in all countries belonging to the European Union (EU) energy performance regulations relate to thermal bridges but approaches and in particular the minimum requirements are significantly different from each other. In Romania the calculation procedures are defined in the "Thermal regulations" (C107-2005) and in the "Methodology of Calculation of the Energy Performance of Buildings Mc 001/part 1, 2, 3 – 2006" taking into account all CEN standards available and Romanian research activity results, both for new and existing buildings and also for residential and non-residential buildings.

According to the European Commission for Standardization (CEN), CEN standards documents will form the equivalent national standards, they are not required and therefore actual energy performance requirements come from national norms. Role of CEN-EPBD standards is to provide a common European concept and common methods for the preparation and certification of the energy performance of buildings .

The thermal performance evaluation method used in our country lies in "Methodology for calculating the energy performance of buildings" Mc 001-2006. This methodology aims to establish evaluation methods and energy performance certification for both new buildings and for existing ones, with different functions. Technical Regulation also establishes performance requirements and standard values / reference values levels of thermal performance of the building and construction elements that make up the building envelope, differentiated for the different categories and types of buildings, climates, etc. (C107-2005).

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2. Materials/Methods

Corrected thermal resistance is determined at construction elements with inhomogeneous composition, it take into account the influence of thermal bridges on the value of thermal resistance determined from a unidirectional flow field calculation.

For the calculation of corrected thermal resistance there were being considered 3 cases. The first two cases (Case 1 and Case 2) were based on manual calculation, and the third one on automatic calculation.

Values were determined for different constructive systems.

First solution adopted was made of steel columns: HEA 240 which were embedded in three types of masonry: Porotherm ceramic hollow masonry of 25 cm ($\lambda=0.15$ W/mK), autoclaved aerated concrete of 25 cm ($\lambda=0.25$ W/mK) and solid brick of 24 cm ($\lambda=0.50$ W/mK). There were being considered solutions where the walls were assumed to be thermally isolated with: 10 cm, 15 cm, 20 cm of mineral wool ($\lambda=0.044$ W/mK).

Fig. 1. - Horizontal section through exterior wall and steel columns HEA 240 with insulation

For the second solution were being considered another type of columns and masonry. There were been used HEA 280 columns embedded in Porotherm ceramic hollow masonry of 30cm , autoclaved aerated concrete masonry of 30 cm and solid brick masonry of 29 cm.

The thermal conductivity of the materials were being considered the same in both constructive solutions.

Figure 2 - Horizontal section through exterior wall and steel columns HEA 280 with insulation

2.1. Calculation methods

Case 1 - According to C107-3/2005 – Appendix H

The simplified method can be used below the preliminary and intermediate design stages to determine the corrected specific thermal resistance for building elements consisting of homogeneous layers (MC 001/1-2006).

This method uses a medium value of two thermal resistances: a minimum value R_{\min} and a maximum value R_{\max} .

$$R' = \frac{R_{\max} + R_{\min}}{2} \quad [\text{m}^2\text{K/W}] \quad (1)$$

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Construction element was divided into fragments "mj", which are homogeneous in terms of heat. Each fragment "mj" has a thermal conductivity " λ_{mj} " thick " d_j " a proportion " f_m " and a thermal resistance " R_{mj} ".

R_{max} can be determined using the following:

$$\frac{1}{R_{max}} = \sum \frac{f_m}{R_m} \quad [W/(m^2K)] \quad (2)$$

Where:

$$f_m = \frac{A_m}{A} \quad (3)$$

f_m – proportion of the total area ;

A – total area of the element;

A_m - area of each fragment "mj" ;

R_m – equivalent thermal resistance of each homogeneous layer .

R_{min} can be determined using the following:

$$R_{min} = R_{si} + \sum R_j + R_{se} \quad [m^2K/W] \quad (4)$$

Where:

$$R_j = \frac{d_j}{\lambda_j} \quad [m^2K/W] \quad (5)$$

λ_j - equivalent thermal conductivity of the layer "j", which is calculated with:

$$\lambda_j = \sum \lambda_{mj} \cdot f_m \quad [W/(mK)] \quad (6)$$

Case 2 - According to C107-3/2005 – Appendix J and and Mc001/2006

According to methodology linear thermal transmittance coefficient U' of a construction product in specific interior and exterior conditions can be considered as characteristic for the performance of that product when it is embedded in a part of the construction and can be determined as follows:

$$U' = \frac{1}{R'} = \frac{1}{R} + \frac{\sum (\psi \cdot l)}{A} \quad [W/(m^2K)] \quad (7)$$

R - specific unidirectional thermal resistance for the A surface (m^2K/W);

l_i - the length of thermal bridges included in A surface (m);

ψ - the linear thermal transmittance coefficient (W/mK);

A - surface of the element for which corrected thermal resistance is determined (m^2).

The linear thermal transmittance coefficient can be determined by automatic or manual calculation or can be extracted from the catalogs of thermal bridges (SR EN ISO -10211).

$$\psi = \frac{1}{l} (L^{2D} - \sum U \cdot A) \quad (8)$$

Case 3 – Using automatically software program

Values were determined using of a complex software calculation program UNORM. The program fulfils the requirements in the international standard EN ISO 10211.

Calculation assumptions that were being considered are:

- thermal regime is stationary;
- all physical properties are independent of temperature;
- there is no heat source inside the element considered;
- there is only one indoor thermal environment;
- there are one or two adjacent outdoor thermal environments

3. Results and Discussion

Results were centralized in two tables one for the first solution adopted : HEA 240 steel columns and the second for the solution where there have been used HEA 280 steel columns. In both tables are presented the values for corrected thermal resistance (R') in all considered cases :

Table 1- Corrected thermal resistance values in case there were being used HEA 240 columns

Masonry			CASE 1			CASE 2		CASE 3	
dterm [cm]	λ [W /m·K]	R_{camp} [m ² ·K/W]	Rmin [m ² ·K/W]	Rmax [m ² ·K/W]	R' [m ² ·K/W]	ψ [W/m·K]	R' [m ² ·K/W]	ψ [W/m·K]	R' [m ² ·K/W]
10cm	0.15	4.135	2.986	4.266	3.636	-0.020	4.216	0.028	4.025
	0.25	3.468	2.896	3.612	3.254	-0.030	3.554	0.012	3.434
	0.50	2.948	2.738	3.093	2.915	-0.042	3.038	-0.005	2.958
15cm	0.15	5.271	4.122	5.423	4.772	-0.010	5.352	0.017	5.175
	0.25	4.605	4.032	4.774	4.403	-0.020	4.694	0.007	4.574
	0.50	4.085	3.874	4.260	4.057	-0.026	4.179	-0.003	4.095
20cm	0.15	6.408	5.259	6.574	5.908	-0.014	6.448	0.011	6.305
	0.25	5.741	5.168	5.929	5.526	-0.015	5.826	-0.004	5.706
	0.50	5.221	5.011	5.419	5.185	-0.016	5.305	-0.002	5.236

Figure 3 - Corrected thermal resistance variation using HEA 240 columns

In case when we used steel columns HEA240 calculations results shows there is a difference of 14%-1.3% between the values resulting from manual calculation according to Appendix H, calculations according to Appendix J and program automatic calculation .

In all cases studied the difference between the method used in case 1 (Appendix H) and other two methods (Annex J and UNORM program) is greater than the difference between case 2 and case 3. Thus, if in the case 1 and case 2 is the maximum difference of 14% between 2 and 3 where the maximum difference is 4.53%.

It observe that the differences between values of corrected thermal resistance R' are lower with the increase of the thermal conductivity of masonry (exemple:If we compare case 1 with case 3, for $\lambda=0.15$ [m²·K/W] when we used 10cm of thermal insulation , the reduction coefficient is 13.75% and if we compare case 1 with case 3, for $\lambda=0.50$ [m²·K/W] when we used 10cm of thermal insulation , the reduction coefficient is 4.05% . The same effect if we compare case1 with case 2, for $\lambda=0.15$ [m²·K/W] , the reduction coefficient is 4.53% and for $\lambda=0.15$ [m²·K/W] , the reduction coefficient is 2.60%).

Also the values of the reduction coefficient decreases with the increase of the thickness of thermal insulation (For exemple:If we compare case 1 with case 3, for $\lambda=0.15$ [m²·K/W] when we used 10cm of thermal insulation , the reduction coefficient is 13.75% and if we use 20cm of thermal insulation, for the same $\lambda=0.15$ [m²·K/W], the reduction

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coefficient is 6.40% . The same if we compare 1 with case 2, when we used 10cm of thermal insulation , the reduction coefficient is 4.53% and if we use 20cm of thermal insulation the reduction coefficient is 2.90%)

Table 2- Corrected thermal resistance values in case there were being used HEA 280 columns

Masonry			CASE 1			CASE 2		CASE 3	
dterm [cm]	λ [W /m·K]	R_{camp} [m ² ·K/W]	Rmin [m ² ·K/W]	Rmax [m ² ·K/W]	R' [m ² ·K/W]	ψ [W/m·K]	R' [m ² ·K/W]	ψ [W/m·K]	R' [m ² ·K/W]
10cm	0.15	4.468	2.965	4.641	3.802	-0.022	4.575	0.032	4.320
	0.25	3668	2.881	3.856	3.368	-0.035	3.784	0.013	3.626
	0.50	3.048	2.751	3.233	2.992	-0.050	3.166	-0.007	3.064
15cm	0.15	5.605	4.101	5.804	4.938	-0.016	5.714	0.019	5.456
	0.25	5.850	4.017	5.025	4.504	-0.024	4.920	0.007	4.765
	0.50	4.185	3.887	4.440	4.128	-0.033	4.305	-0.004	4.200
20cm	0.15	6.741	5.238	6.960	6.074	-0.012	6.848	0.013	6.628
	0.25	6.941	5.153	6.187	5.640	-0.018	6.056	0.005	5.907
	0.50	5.321	5.023	5.577	5.261	-0.023	5.432	-0.003	5.337

Figure 4 - Corrected thermal resistance variation using HEA 280 columns

In case when we used steel columns HEA280, analyzing the table and the graph above (Tabel 2 and Figure 4) it can be observed the same phenomen as in the case we steel columns HEA240. Between the values resulting from manual calculation according to Appendix H, calculations according to Appendix J and program automatic calculation the difference varies from 17% to 1.7% .

Maximum difference between case 1 (Appendix H) and the other cases (Annex J and UNORM program) is 16.70% while the maximum difference between case 2 and case 3 is only 5.60%

If we compare case 1 with case 3, for $\lambda=0.25$ [m²·K/W] when we used 15cm of thermal insulation , the reduction coefficient is 8.4% and if we compare case 1 with case 2, for $\lambda=0.50$ [m²·K/W] when we used 15cm of thermal insulation , the reduction coefficient is 4.1% . The same if we compare 1 with case 2, for $\lambda=0.25$ [m²·K/W] , the reduction coefficient is 3.1% and for $\lambda=0.25$ [m²·K/W] , the reduction coefficient is 2.40%).

Also the values of the reduction coefficient decreases with the increase of the thickness of thermal insulation (exemple:If we compare case 1 with case 3, for $\lambda=0.15$ [m²·K/W] when we used 10cm of thermal insulation , the reduction coefficient is 16.89% and if we use 20cm of thermal insulation, for the same $\lambda=0.15$ [m²·K/W], the reduction

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coefficient is 11.13% . The same if we compare 2 with case 3, when we used 10cm of thermal insulation , the reduction coefficient is 5.57% and if we use 20cm of thermal insulation the reduction coefficient is 3.20%).

4. Conclusions

In cases of predimensioning , there can be use manual calculation version according to Appendix H, much faster than the other options.

If calculations for issuing energy certificates where being required with rigorous and accurate results, it is recommended variant manual calculation according to Appendix J or automatic calculation programs.

5. References

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